

What Fans Think Greek Myth Smells Like sea, smoke, and flower shampoo

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1 Introduction

Scents are intimate: from your mother’s cooking to your lover’s armpit, smells are often connected to personal experiences and feelings (Glausiusz 2008). Furthermore, smells often imply a value judgment, with things we like smelling good and things we dislike smelling bad, at least metaphorically (Jaquet 2024). In literature, smells have also been found to correlate with characters’ social class (Al assali et al. 2024). The ways smells feature in fanfiction – a genre of online literature often deeply engaged with the emotional and sensory dimensions of fictional experiences and with value judgements of cultural materials – thus offers a path to understanding fans’ intimate connections with the narratives that fanfiction rewrites. Research has shown that online fan communities often engage with scents as a way to achieve closeness to their object of fandom (Yodovich 2022). This analysis also furthers the understanding of contemporary audiences’ relationship to Antiquity, since “olfaction [is] a potent tool for understanding and evaluating the Greco-Roman world” (Toner and Bradley 2015). In this paper, we therefore use the Odeuropa information extraction system (version 2, Menini 2024) to extract the “smellscape” (Porteous 1985) in a corpus of fanfiction about Greek mythology. We examine associations between smells, character gender and storyworld by comparing the smell-properties of male and female characters, and of stories situated in ancient and contemporary settings.

2 Dataset

We use a dataset of fanfiction in the *Ancient Greek Religion and Lore* fandom on Archive of Our Own (AO3), one of the largest online repositories for English-language fanfiction. The dataset contains 5,154 stories and is ±28 million words long. All stories are in English and were completed at the time of data collection. The dataset, which contains all works of fanfiction on this particular platform in this specific fandom that were publically available at the time, was described in previous work (Neugarten 2024).

3 Pipeline

To recognise smell references in the corpus, we use the Odeuropa information extraction system v2 (Menini 2024). This system extracts references to smell and accompanying elements such as descriptions of the smell (Quality/Evoked Odorant), agents perceiving the smell (Perceiver) and the entity emitting the smell (Odour Carrier/Smell Source). To create the system, a BERT-model trained on contemporary text was fine-tuned on 85 manually annotated English documents published between 1600 and 1920 across a range of different categories such as travelogues, medicine & botany treatises, and household (recipe) books. We use the English fine-tuned en-model-v2 in multi-task setting.

Menini’s model is “the first system for multilingual olfactory information extraction” (Menini 2024, p. 14625). On the benchmark data, it achieves F1 scores between .88 and .40 on the different frame elements. For the experiments reported in this abstract, we focus on the elements ‘Odour Carrier’/‘Smell Source’, ‘Smell Quality’, and ‘Perceiver’ for which the F1 scores on the benchmark are 0.48, 0.76, and 0.51 respectively.

In our data, the pipeline has recognised 2,106 Odour Carriers, 13,748 Smell Sources, 6,776 Smell Qualities, 6,370 Perceivers, 742 Times, 1,880 Locations, and 1,822 Effects. We then sorted these results into subsets for comparative analysis. Sorting criteria are described in Appendix A.

Figure 3: Smell Qualities by Character Gender

Men were more often detected as the perceivers of smells in both the male and female subsets: the sum of the absolute frequency of the words he/his/him as perceiver was 845 in the female-subset (against 684 for she/her/hers) and 848 in the male-subset (against only 70 for she/her/hers), although we did not count named entities in this comparison. It is possible that this gendered imbalance in the role of smell-perceiver also indicates a gendered power imbalance in character dynamics, since smelling someone may have predatory connotations.

4.2 Stinky Storyworlds

In fanfiction situated in mythological storyworlds, blood, burning and death are among the most frequently-mentioned smell sources (Figure 4a), while cosmetic products, especially shampoo and perfume, are much more prevalent sources of scents in contemporary settings (Figure 4b). The smells associated with the mythological universe – and their qualities, (Figure 5a) – bring to mind the cultural construction of a less-civilized era, where violence was commonplace and ‘fetid’, ‘putrid’, ‘metallic’ and ‘foul’ odours assault the senses. Thus, the observation that smells are an important tool to “make sense of our past and present” (Bembibre and Strlič 2022, p. 1), and to emphasize differences between these eras, applies in fanfiction about the mythological past as well.

Figure 4: Smell Sources by Storyworld Era

References

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A Appendix: Selection Criteria for Subsets

A.1 Male Characters

Our male-character-subset contained all smells detected in sentences with any of the following words or character names. These character names come from the most-prevalent character-tags in the metadata and were manually annotated by gender, resulting in a 4.168-row dataset.

- he
- him
- Achilles
- Adonis
- Aegisthus
- Aeneas
- Agamemnon
- Aizawa
- Ajax
- Albus
- Alecto
- Alfred
- Anteros
- Ares
- Arthur
- Asclepius
- Asterion
- Asterius
- Astyanax
- Atlas
- Aziraphale
- Ben
- Bobby
- Bruce
- Castiel
- Castor
- Charon
- Chiron
- Clark
- Clay
- Clint
- Cronus
- Crowley
- Cupid
- Daedalus
- Daidalos
- Damian
- Darcy
- Dean
- Derek
- Diomedes
- Dionusius
- Dionysus
- Enjolras
- Ephaistos
- Epimetheus
- Erakles
- Erik
- Ermes
- Eros
- Gabriel
- Ganymede
- Grantaire
- Hades
- Hannibal
- Harry
- Hector
- Helenus
- Helios
- Hephaestus
- Heracles
- Hercules
- Hermes
- Heron
- Hyacinth
- Hyacinthus
- Hypnos
- Icarus
- Ikaros
- Isaac
- James
- Jason
- John
- Kronos
- Loki
- Louis
- Lucifer
- Menelaos
- Menelaus
- Merlin
- Minos
- Mycroft
- Narcissus
- Neoptolemus
- Nestor
- Nico
- Odin
- Odinn
- Odusseus
- Odysseus
- Orion
- Orpheus
- Pan
- Paris
- Patroclus
- Patroklos
- Pegasus
- Peleus
- Pentheus
- Percy
- Perseus
- Peter
- Phobos
- Pollux
- Poseidon
- Priam
- Prometheus
- Pygmalion
- Remus
- Ron
- Sherlock
- Sirius
- Sisyphus
- Steve
- Stiles
- Telemachus
- Thanatos
- Theseus
- Thor
- Thorr
- Tim
- Tony
- Triton
- Tundareus
- Typhon
- Uranus
- Wilbur
- Zagreus
- Zephyrus
- Zeus

A.2 Female Characters

Our female-character-subset contained all smells detected in sentences with any of the following words or character names. These character names come from the most-prevalent character-tags in the metadata and were manually annotated by gender, resulting in a 8.556-row dataset.

- she
- her
- Allison
- Amphitrite
- Andromache
- Annabeth
- Antigone
- Antilochus
- Arachne
- Ariadne
- Artemis
- Atalanta
- Atropos
- Aphrodite
- Athena
- Bianca
- Briseis
- Calliope
- Callisto
- Calypso
- Cassandra
- Circe
- Clio
- Clotho
- Clytemnestra
- Daphne
- Deidameia
- Deiphobus
- Demeter
- Diana
- Echo
- Eileithyia
- Ekate
- Electra
- Elene
- Emma
- Enyo
- Eos
- Eris
- Estelle
- Estia
- Euridike
- Eurydice
- Gaia
- Galatea
- Ginny
- Harmonia
- Hebe
- Hecate
- Hecuba
- Helen
- Hera
- Hermione
- Hesione
- Hestia
- Inanna
- Iris
- Iphigenia
- Jane
- Cassandra
- Kore
- Lachesis
- Laura
- Leda
- Leto
- Luna
- Lydia
- Maia
- Makaria
- Mary
- Medea
- Medusa
- Megaera
- Melinoe
- Melpomene
- Metis
- Midorya
- Minthe
- Mnemosyne
- Moirai
- muses
- Natasha
- Nyx
- Pandora
- Pasiphae
- Peggy
- Penelope
- Pepper
- Persephone
- Psyche
- Rey
- Rhea
- Sally
- Sansa
- Selene
- Seraphim
- Thalia
- Themis
- Thetis
- Wanda

A.3 Storyworld Subsets

Our two storyworld subsets contained smells detected in fanfiction with any of the following user-added additional tags. Mythological storyworld-tags (left) resulted in a 1.457-row dataset. Contemporary storyworld-tags (right) resulted in a 6.471-row dataset.

- References to Ancient Greek Religion & Lore
- Greek Mythology - Freeform
- Trojan War
- Alternate Universe
- Alternate Universe - Canon Divergence
- Alternate Universe - Modern Setting